

lated six-membered compounds¹. Aluminium chloride forms a relatively low melting double salt with alkali metal halides and the melt is generally used for this type of cyclocondensation. We reported² the synthesis of 5,12-dihydroxy-6,11-dioxo-1-azanaphthalenes by the cyclocondensation of phthalic anhydride with 5,8-dimethoxy quinolines and 5,8-dimethoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinolines in presence of sodium aluminium chloride melt. Now we report the synthesis of a new 1,4-diazanaphthalene (3) by the cyclocondensation of phthalic anhydride with 5,8-dimethoxy-diphenylquinoxaline (2).

The reaction of benzil with 1,4-dimethoxy-2,3-diaminobenzene gave 2 in good yield^{3,4}. The cyclocondensation of 2 with phthalic anhydride has been carried out in presence of sodium aluminium chloride melt to give 3 and 5,8-dihydroxy-2,3-diphenylquinoxaline (4). Structure of 3 was settled through spectral analysis.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Thomas-Hoover melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu-UV 260 spectrophotometer, ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR-1710 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra on a Jeol FX-100 (100 MHz) spectrometer and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D 300 spectrometer using the electron impact method (70 eV).

5,12-Dihydroxy-6,11-dioxo-2,3-diphenyl-1,4-diazanaphthalene (3): To the melt of aluminium chloride (4.56 g, 0.03 mol) and sodium chloride (0.90 g, 0.015 mol) kept at 190–95°, were added 5,8-dimethoxy-2,3-diphenylquinoxaline (2; 0.5 g, 0.0015 mol) and phthalic anhydride (1; 0.44 g, 0.003 mol) and mixed under a nitrogen atmosphere. After heating for 1 h at the above temperature, the mixture was cooled in an ice-bath and a saturated solution of oxalic acid (50 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. The solution was stirred for 3 h and extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 100 ml) and

Synthesis of 5,12-Dihydroxy-6,11-dioxo-2,3-diphenyl-1,4-diazanaphthalene by Cyclocondensation†

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THE cyclocondensation of phthalic anhydride and phthaloyl chloride with 1,4-dimethoxybenzene, 5,8-dimethoxynaphthalene and related compounds is an important method for the synthesis of 1,4-dihydroxy-9,10-dioxoanthracene and related annu-

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dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4). The residue was purified by column chromatography over silica gel and elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 3) gave an yellow crystalline compound (4 ; 25%), m.p. 174° (lit.³ $174-75^\circ$). Further elution with benzene yielded 3, which was crystallised from benzene, (10%), m.p. $258-59^\circ$; $\lambda_{\text{max}}(\epsilon_{\text{max}})$ (CH_2Cl_2) 268.0 (20.1), 355.0(13.2), 456.0(7.1), 482.4(8.8) and 515.4 nm (6.5); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 620, 1 585, 1 460, 1 310, 1 120, 1 013, 800 and 760 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 7.36 (6H, m, 3', 4', 5'-Ph), 7.65 (4H, m, 2', 6'-Ph), 7.84 (2H, m, H-8, H-9), 8.48 (2H, m, H-7, H-10) and 14.68 (2H, s, 5-, 12-OH); m/z (rel. int.) 444.0 (M^+ , 33.2), 443.0(100.0), 442.0(12.5), 340.0(5.0), 238.0(27.5), 237.0(10.0) and 236.0(27.4).

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